

Statistical Analysis of 2D Projective Shape Data Using a Novel Infimum Dimension Nash Embedding

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Abstract

A statistical analysis of manifold-valued data often requires an embedding into an Euclidean space of some kind. A good embedding will retain enough information to solve the problem at hand. In this regard, an isometric or Nash embedding is often desired since it preserves path lengths, angles, areas and volumes. Furthermore, we would also want an embedding to be equivariant so that it preserves geometric features associated with the natural homogeneity of the manifold. The Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding is an equivariant embedding, in fact the only embedding, used in the analysis of 2D projective shape data, at the present time. In this manuscript we consider a novel equivariant Nash embedding into a Euclidean space of a lower dimension than that for the Veronese-Whitney embedding. In fact, it is shown in Patrangenaru and Paige (2023) that the novel equivariant Nash embedding places projective shape data in a Euclidean space with lowest possible dimension. We compare the performance of novel Nash embedding-based statistical techniques with those based on the VW embedding.

Key Words: Extrinsic shape analysis, Nash embedding, Nonparametric tests, Two-dimensional projective shape analysis

1. Pinhole Camera Model

Digital image data plays a vital role in engineering, the mathematical sciences, the biomedical sciences, and many other science and technology fields. Much of this image data comes from a security or cell-phone camera. For these types of image acquisition systems knowledge about camera calibration and scene structure is often unknown. In this uncalibrated camera setting one cannot correct an image for perspective effects associated with the placement of the imaging system relative to the object of the interest. These perspective effects are however relatively easy to describe once one adopts the pinhole camera model. Furthermore, the pinhole camera is considered a good approximation to a well-focused imaging system.

Consider the following diagram of a pinhole camera.

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Here the hole or aperture through which light passes is the pinhole. The back wall of the camera is the image plane. In the pinhole camera model the pinhole represents the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 . With this model we see that a point $(X, Y, Z)^T$ in \mathbb{R}^3 is projected to a point in \mathbb{R}^2 , call it $(x, y)^T$ on the back wall of the camera, which is known as its image plane. For instance the bottom of the tree above is projected to a point on top of the inverted two-dimensional figure on the image plane. More formally this is known as a perspective projection or perspectivity. Note that as a mapping from \mathbb{R}^3 to \mathbb{R}^3 the perspectivity maps $(X, Y, Z)^T$ to $(x, y, -d)^T$ where d represents the distance from the camera aperture to the image plane. The $-d$ value represents the fact that the image of the tree on the image plane is inverted. Furthermore, since one does not take into account the distance from the tree to the camera, or the distance from the pinhole to the image plane then vector $(x, y, -d)^T$ is identified up to a non-zero scalar multiple which is our “axial space” or projective space representation of $(X, Y, Z)^T$ on the image plane. Hence then we can represent our image point as $(-x/d, -y/d, 1)^T$ or more simply as inhomogenous coordinate $(x, y, 1)^T$. Note that this last representation is justified when one corrects upside-down image with the following transformation $(x, y)^T \rightarrow (-x, -y)^T$.

2. Projective Space

In projective geometry two non-zero vectors in \mathbb{R}^3

$$x_1 = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} \\ x_{2,1} \\ x_{3,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad x_2 = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,2} \\ x_{2,2} \\ x_{3,2} \end{bmatrix}$$

are equivalent if they differ by a non-zero scalar multiple. The equivalence class of $x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}$ is labeled $[x]$.

Definition: The set of all such equivalence classes is the projective space $P(\mathbb{R}^3)$ associated with \mathbb{R}^3 meaning that

$$P(\mathbb{R}^3) = \{[x_1, x_2, x_3]; x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}\}.$$

Note that Projective space $P(\mathbb{R}^3)$ is equivalent to \mathbb{S}^2 , the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 , with the antipodal points identified and $P(\mathbb{R}^3)$ is also denoted as $\mathbb{R}P^2$. Finally, $\mathbb{R}P^2$ is an example of a non-linear space known as a manifold.

3. Shape Spaces

Invariant recognition of objects is an important long-standing problem in computer vision. Projective shape analysis provides a method for making statistical inference about images which is invariant under projective transformations.

3.1 Projective Shape Space

In this section we review some of the basic concepts and definitions of projective shape analysis; see Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005) for more details.

Definition: An arbitrary projective transformation of a configuration, or k -ad, of points in \mathbb{R}^2 , denoted as X , in homogenous coordinates is of the form

$$g_P(X) = \left(\left[P \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right], \dots, \left[P \begin{pmatrix} x_k \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right] \right)$$

where $P \in GL(3, \mathbb{R})$, the group of 3×3 invertible matrices.

Definition: The projective shape of a k -ad X is the orbit of that k -ad under projective transformations $P \in GL(3, \mathbb{R})$ i.e. $[X] = \{g_P(X) : P \in GL(3, \mathbb{R})\}$.

Definition: Two configurations, or k -ads, of points in \mathbb{R}^2 have the same the projective shape if they differ by a projective transformation of \mathbb{R}^2 .

4. Embeddings

Extrinsic shape analysis involves embedding manifold-valued data into an Euclidean space of some kind. An embedding of an object X in object Y involves an injective structure-preserving map from X into Y . Here structure has the meaning of a set, or collection of sets, possessing some additional features. In our work we are concerned with embeddings that preserve particular geometric features. For example, one naturally thinks of a sphere \mathbb{S}^2 as being embedded in \mathbb{R}^3 with the identity embedding which, incidentally, preserves path lengths.

Here we want to choose an embedding into a Euclidean space (vector space with an inner product) which preserves a substantial amount of the geometry of $\mathbb{R}P^2$. In this regard, an isometric embedding is often desired since it preserves path lengths, angles, areas and volumes. The Nash Embedding Theorem (Nash, 1956) tells us that any manifold with a Riemannian structure can be isometrically embedded in some Euclidean space of high enough dimension. Note that this theorem simply proves the existence of an isometric embedding and does not provide an algorithm for deriving such an embedding which remains an open problem for the vast majority of Riemannian manifolds. Nonetheless, Paige and Patrangenaru (2023) provide a Nash embedding for $\mathbb{R}P^2$ which is then used to derive an Nash embedding for $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$.

4.1 Veronese-Whitney Embedding

The Veronese-Whitney (VW) embedding is the only embedding used in projective shape analysis prior to Nash embedding from Paige and Patrangenaru (2023). It is given as

$$j([x]) = xx^T. \quad (1)$$

where $x^T x = 1$ and it embeds $\mathbb{R}P^2$ into $Sym(3, \mathbb{R})$, the Euclidean space of 3×3 symmetric matrices with real entries. Note that while (VW) embedding is equivariant under orthogonal group $O(3)$.

4.2 Infimum Dimension Nash Embedding for $\mathbb{R}P^2$

In Paige and Patrangenaru (2023) it is derived as

$$\iota([x]) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2}(x_1^2 - x_2^2) \\ x_1 x_3 \\ \frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}}(2x_3^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2) \\ x_2 x_3 \\ x_1 x_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

This embedding is also equivariant under the orthogonal group action of $O(3)$.

5. Tangential Components

The tangential components for the VW embedded data is given in Patrangenaru and Ellingson (2015). Here we summarize the discussion of tangential components for the Nash embedding from Paige and Patrangenaru (2023).

Let $Y_a = \iota(X_a)$, with $a = 1, \dots, n$ for Nash embedding ι , then since the sample mean \bar{Y} ;

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \iota(X_i) \quad (2)$$

lies in the ambient space it converges almost surely to mean $\tilde{\mu} = E[\iota(X_1)]$, the expectation of the embedded $\mathbb{R}P^2$ random variable. Let P be the projection map from the set of ι nonfocal points in \mathbb{R}^5 to $\iota(\mathbb{R}P^2) \subset \mathbb{R}^5$. If P is regarded as a differentiable function from \mathbb{R}^5 to \mathbb{R}^5 , then the range of the differential $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}$ is valued in T , the tangent space to $\iota(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ at $P(\tilde{\mu})$. Note that random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ has a degenerate covariance matrix. To correct for this we consider the decomposition of $\iota(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ in \mathbb{R}^5 into its tangential component and orthogonal complement (w.r.t. an orthonormal basis of T) in the tangent space to $\iota(\mathbb{R}P^2)$ in \mathbb{R}^5 at $P(\tilde{\mu})$. Denote the tangential component of differential random vector $DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$ as $\tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$. Then for large n ,

$$\sqrt{n} \{P(\bar{Y}) - P(\tilde{\mu})\} \approx \sqrt{n} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu})$$

Furthermore, as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sqrt{n} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}) \xrightarrow{d} N_2(0, \tilde{\Sigma})$$

where

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = Cov\{\tan DP_{\mu}(Y_1 - \tilde{\mu})\}$$

is the covariance of the tangential component of the differential map for a single random observation.

In extrinsic shape analysis tests are based on asymptotic chi-square statistics generated from tangential components. For instance, the one sample test $H_0: \tilde{\mu} = \tilde{\mu}_0$ is of the form

$$n \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}_0}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}_0)^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \tan DP_{\tilde{\mu}_0}(\bar{Y} - \tilde{\mu}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_2^2$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}$ is the sample covariance of

$$\{\tan DP_{\mu_0}(Y_i - \tilde{\mu}_0) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}.$$

Under the equality of m extrinsic means in $\mathbb{R}P^2$ with independent samples

$$\sum_{j=1}^m n_j \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y})^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y}) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_{2(m-1)}^2$$

where now \bar{Y} is the sample mean of the combined data sets and $\hat{\Sigma}$ is now the sample covariance of

$$\{\tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(Y_{ji} - \bar{Y}) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n_j \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

Finally, under the equality of m extrinsic means in $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$ with independent samples

$$\sum_{j=1}^m n_j \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y})^T \hat{\Sigma}_k^{-1} \tan DP_{\bar{Y}}(\bar{Y}_j - \bar{Y}) \xrightarrow{d} \chi_{2q(m-1)}^2$$

where $\hat{\Sigma}_k$ is the sample covariance of concatenated tangential components.

5.1 Application

We considered the BBC actor's data from Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005) which consists of seven frontal views and seven side views of the **same** actor posing in different disguises.

On each image six landmarks were recorded consisting of the four corners of the eyes, “canthus,” and two end points of the lips, “mouth edge points” as shown in the image below.

Here the four eye-corner landmarks were taken to be the projective frame which resulted in a 2-ad of $\mathbb{R}P^2$ data points for each image. The data is given in Table 3 of Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005) who considered a level $\alpha = 0.05$ parametric test and a bootstrap test for difference in mean projective shapes of the frontal and side views. Both methodologies lead to the same conclusion that the frontal and side views are of the same actor. Here, we came to the same conclusion for the Nash embedding-based and VW-based test statistics which both have observed values of 4.896 with a cutoff of $\chi_{4,0.95}^2 = 9.488$.

6. Distance-based Testing Procedures

6.1 Multiresponse Permutation Procedure

We consider the two sample Multiresponse Permutation Procedure (MRPP) (Mielke and Berry, 2001) for random objects $\{X_i\}$. Here, the two sample MRPP statistic is given as

$$\delta = \frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2} \xi_1 + \frac{n_2}{n_1 + n_2} \xi_2$$

where

$$\xi_i = \frac{1}{\binom{n_i}{2}} \sum_{\substack{I < J \\ \{(i,j) \in S_i\}}} d^2(X_i, X_j),$$

$d(\cdot)$ is the chosen distance function, S_i is the collection of indices for the random objects X_i in sample i , and n_i is the number of k-ads in this sample. The p-value for the observed MRPP statistic, δ_0 , is obtained by computing the value of the MRPP statistic under all possible permutations of $n_1 + n_2$ data points into two samples containing n_1 and n_2 data points, respectively.

6.2 Extrinsic Energy Statistic Approximate Permutation Procedure

Guo et al. (2023) define the Extrinsic Energy Statistic (EE-test) as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{\iota, n_1, n_2} = & \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{m=1}^{n_1} \|\iota(X_i) - \iota(Y_m)\| - \frac{n_2}{nn_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{h=1}^{n_1} \|\iota(X_i) - \iota(X_h)\| \\ & - \frac{n_1}{nn_2} \sum_{l=1}^{n_2} \sum_{m=1}^{n_2} \|\iota(Y_l) - \iota(Y_m)\| \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $X_1, \dots, X_{n_1}, Y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2}$ are iid random objects and ι is the embedding of choice. The p-value for this test was computed via the nonparametric bootstrap, which is an approximate permutation test. This is an extension of the Two-Sample E-statistic proposed by Szekely and Rizzo (2004) for Euclidean data.

7. Application and Monte Carlo Studies

Here we consider the performance of the above permutation procedures where we use embedded data of four types: (i) VW embedded data (VW Dist.); (ii) VW tangential components (VW Tan.); (iii) Nash embedded data (Nash Dist.) and (vi) Nash tangential components (Nash Tan.). Note that Frobenius distance was assumed for the MRPP statistic in all settings. Also, the EE-test applied to tangential component data effectively assumed the identity embedding for ι in equation (3).

7.1 P-values the BBC Actors Data

	VW Dist.	VW Tan.	Nash Dist.	Nash Tan.
MRPP	0.0214	0.0234	0.0231	0.0238
EE-test	0.0271	0.0232	0.0226	0.0233

Here all of the eight procedures incorrectly found a difference in mean projective shapes of the frontal and side views.

7.2 Simulated Power Values for Synthetic Facial Landmark Data

We consider a Monte Carlo study involved simulated facial landmark data. This method of simulation was also considered in Paige and Patrangenaru (2023) albeit for different statistical procedures than we consider here. Our Monte Carlo study simulates from the two populations generated by the randomly perturbing the 9 facial landmarks for the average

white American male and female faces (Face Research Lab in the Institute of Neuroscience and Psychology at the University of Glasgow) as shown below

For each simulation run these pixel perturbations were bivariate and independent uniform realizations each over the interval $(-\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$. For each set of gender landmarks total of 4 bivariate uniform realizations were used. This is because we assumed certain symmetries in these perturbations in that landmarks 1 and 4 had the same perturbation, landmarks 2 and 3 had the same perturbation, landmarks 5, 6 and 7 have their own perturbation, and landmarks 8 and 9 have their own perturbation. In our Monte Carlo study we had 1,000 runs in which independent samples of size 30 for each set of gender landmarks was performed.

For these we took the four corners of the pictures to be our projective frame from which we generated our projective coordinates; see Mardia and Patrangenaru (2005). These corners are not marked in the images above. Also ε was set equal to 40 so the pixel perturbations in vertical and horizontal directions could be as large as 40 pixel units. Numerical experimentation and visual inspection indicated that this might be a reasonable amount of natural landmark variation from person to person.

Note that the simulated significance levels for the eight procedures we consider are not shown but did not differ significantly from nominal value 0.05. The table below gives the simulated power values for each of the eight procedures we consider.

	VW Dist.	VW Tan.	Nash Dist.	Nash Tan.
MRPP	0.809	0.823	0.803	0.856
EE-test	0.811	0.818	0.803	0.863

Note the two procedures using The Nash Tan. data are statistically significantly more powerful than the other six procedures.

8. Conclusions

We consider a novel equivariant Nash embedding for $\mathbb{R}P^2$ into a Euclidean space of a lower dimension than that for the Veronese-Whitney embedding. Note a q -fold Cartesian product of infimum dimension Nash embeddings $\mathbb{R}P^2$ is not itself guaranteed to be a infimum dimension Nash embedding for product space $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$. Nonetheless, we found that our Nash embedding for $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$ into $(\mathbb{R}^5)^q$ performed as well and in some cases better than the classical VW emdedding for $(\mathbb{R}P^2)^q$ into $(Sym(3, \mathbb{R}))^q$. However, Nash-embedded space $(\mathbb{R}^5)^q$ lends itself easily to interpretability and to further analysis and visualization with traditional statistical techniques whereas the VW-embedded space $(Sym(3, \mathbb{R}))^q$ is a rather esoteric space that does not led itself to further analyses.

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